

Digital Inequality: Implications for Online Communities and Platforms

Research Synthesis by Floor Fiers and Aaron Shaw

The Internet presents immense opportunities for education, connection, and community building, but such opportunities are not equally available to all. What are the implications of inequalities of digital access and participation for online communities and platforms?

1. Internet connectivity is not universal; neither is online participation.

Contrary to public perceptions that “everyone” is on the Internet, differences of connectivity shape who gets online and what they do there. According to 2021 Pew Research, 7% of U.S. adults do not use the Internet at all and 15% primarily use or depend on their smartphones for Internet access. Many people struggle to maintain Internet access from a consistent location or set of devices because they use borrowed or shared equipment [1]. For others, technology or connectivity might be unstable. This can lead them to accumulate back-up devices, seek access through a public computer (e.g., at a library), or be entirely offline for periods of time. While programs exist to expand Internet access, such as affordable broadband plans, such initiatives often fail to increase connectivity among low-income households [2]. These inequalities limit the ability of many people to participate in activities online.

2. Participation requires awareness of online environments and tools.

Specific kinds of knowledge are required to participate in different online spaces. Understanding the different requirements a person needs to pass through before they can participate (fully) in a specific community or platform reveals barriers they might face. For example, knowing of a platform or a specific set of features is always a prerequisite for participation. As of 2016, almost all U.S. adult Internet users had visited Wikipedia, but only about one in three knew it was possible to edit Wikipedia [5]. What if it were also necessary to create an account with two-factor authentication in order to join the project? Every barrier like this narrows the pool of potential participants in ways that may or may not align with community goals and values.

Figure 1. Visualization of the relationships between Internet skills, education level, and the probabilities of participating on gig economy platforms. People with higher levels of internet skills and education are more likely to have completed each of four steps necessary to participate (having heard of, visited, had an account, or completed a task on gig economy sites). See [4] for details of the study design, analysis, and additional interpretation.

3. Digital skills enable online participation.

The extent to which a person ends up participating online also depends on their abilities and skills to do so. Research uses the term “digital skills” [6] to refer to the competencies that matter in the context of online activities. For example, people vary in their ability to open an email inbox or create an account on a site. Similarly, they differ in their ability to recognize scams or comprehend technical features like algorithmic recommendations of content. As a result of divergences in digital skills, some people are more likely to act on the opportunities for participation in communities and platforms as well as to minimize the potential downsides of such participation. Digital skills empower people to capitalize on their technology use and engage online in beneficial ways, such as building and maintaining social connections, cultivating professional networks, identifying and pursuing legitimate opportunities).

4. Resources and skills shape who is present and active online.

Among those who are connected and across the spectrum of digital skills, online activity remains unequal along almost every dimension in terms of who participates and how much [3], [4]. These inequalities include a variety of online behaviors, such as platform adoption and content contribution. People from privileged backgrounds (e.g., [people with more education](#) [5]) are more likely to possess digital skills and also more likely to access and benefit from opportunities in online communities and digital platforms. Resources like education and skills often reinforce each other, compounding existing social inequalities in online spaces. See Figure 1 for an example: people with higher levels of education and higher levels of digital skills are more likely to have completed multiple steps necessary to pursue work through gig economy sites.

5. People acquire digital skills through ongoing, non-linear, and distinct pathways.

Building the skills needed for different online environments is an ongoing and non-linear process. Rather than learning to navigate a platform or community all at once, people proceed unevenly. Their learning pathways vary widely. Some explore a space through trial and error, testing different strategies to achieve their goals. Others might prefer to browse documentation, interact with others who share their experiences, or learn from a friend. The evolution of site interfaces and features makes it necessary to engage in continuous learning and adaptation. Design changes might render some existing skills obsolete, while demanding the acquisition of new expertise.

Community Strategy and Design Recommendations

Examine who is and who is not present in your community.

Internet access and online participation are unequal along many dimensions. To identify gaps, assess both who is present and who is absent on a platform or in a community. You might think about differences in participation along the (intersecting) lines of geography, age, gender, race, ethnicity, income, and ability status. Surveys and profile data of participants are helpful tools to identify patterns, but incomplete because they do not contain information about non-participants. Consider gathering complementary information from additional sources (e.g., market research, national surveys, focus groups with non-participants) for insights into non-participation.

Evaluate the steps, skills, and paths to becoming a community member.

Joining and participating in a community often entails a mix of hard requirements (e.g., you have to learn about the existence of the community and be able to interact with specific tools from specific devices to post/contribute) as well as softer, less crucial skills or experiences that might help, but are not required. Community members and leaders should identify potential barriers to participation along with the pathways available to navigate those barriers. Keep in mind that current community members and participants can only tell one side of the story here because they successfully navigated the barriers already.

Craft access and inclusion strategies that align with the resources and skills needed to participate fully.

If, after identifying gaps and barriers to participation, you determine that changes are needed, develop and evaluate inclusion strategies along similar lines. For example, enabling users to log in easily from multiple devices or toggle bandwidth requirements might make it possible for people with connectivity constraints to participate, but the complexity of navigating settings changes still might prevent them from doing so fully. Consider adopting defaults optimized for usability, reducing the number of changes, and communicating changes clearly to make digital skill building easier, particularly for those with less time or resources at hand.

Facilitate learning, experimentation, and knowledge sharing.

People learn in different ways, so provide multiple avenues for building digital skills as well as opportunities for knowledge sharing. You might encourage experimentation by allowing users to undo actions easily and providing feedback on their behaviors (e.g., examples of how others use the site). Forums or chat spaces can also support informal learning and knowledge exchange. In facilitating peer-to-peer communication, online communities have the potential to become hotspots for digital skills creation.

References

- [1] A. Gonzales, "The contemporary US digital divide: from initial access to technology maintenance," *Information, Communication & Society*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 234–248, Feb. 2016, doi:10.1080/1369118X.2015.1050438.
- [2] H. Galperin, "A Failed Regulatory Remedy? An Empirical Examination of Affordable Broadband Plan Obligations," *International Journal of Communication*, vol. 16, no. 0, Art. no. 0, Nov. 2022.
- [3] S. Livingstone and E. Helsper, "Gradations in digital inclusion: children, young people and the digital divide," *New Media & Society*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 671–696, Aug. 2017, doi:10.1177/146144807080335.
- [4] F. Fiers, A. Shaw, and E. Hargittai, "Generous Attitudes and Online Participation," *Journal of Quantitative Description: Digital Media*, vol. 1, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.51685/jqd.2021.008>.
- [5] A. Shaw and E. Hargittai, "The Pipeline of Online Participation Inequalities: The Case of Wikipedia Editing," *J Commun*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 143–168, Feb. 2018, doi:10.1093/joc/jqx003.
- [6] E. Hargittai, Ed., *Handbook of Digital Inequality*. Cheltenham, UK; Northampton, MA, USA: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2021.